

UNDERSTANDING THE CHALLENGES OF NEWLY HIRED TEACHERS DURING THE LIMITED FACE TO FACE EDUCATION

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Understanding the Challenges of Newly Hired Teachers during the Limited Face to Face Education

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Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic had an impact on schools all over the world. The new norm in academia was a reduction in teaching and learning activities. Teachers around the world were challenged to come up with innovative ways to help students during the COVID-19 pandemic. This phenomenological study aimed to understand the challenges faced by newly hired teachers during the limited face-to-face classes for the school year 2022-2023. Data gathered from participants may provide useful insight on how educators navigate the phenomenon despite being unprepared. The study utilized a qualitative research design using a phenomenological approach with twenty (20) purposefully selected newly hired teachers who experienced the limited face-to-face class. Moreover, the newly hired teachers were from public schools, both in the elementary and high school departments. They underwent in-depth interviews and focus group discussions (FGD) using the validated research instrument. The results of the study were recorded based on the experiences of the teachers, including the challenges they encountered. Emergent themes were formulated: Rejoicing in the Reopening of Classes, Anticipating Challenges, Collaborating with Initiatives, Adhering the Protocol, Meticulous in Tasking and Efficient Communication. On the coping mechanisms, teachers showed strength guided by mission and focus on purpose. Themes were formulated, such as Requesting for Assistance, Receiving Compliments, Sharing of Commitment, Emanating Positivity and Growth, Open Communication and Developing Success. Finally, as to their insights, notable emergent themes were formulated as follows: Receptive to Feedback, Valuing Responsibilities, Accepting Imperfections, Proficiency in Decision Making, Possessing Empathy and Kindness, Enhancing Instructional Methods. The teachers were remarkable in that they aimed to transform the work environment and transfer effective learning to the students, especially here in the Philippines.

Keywords: *educational management, challenges, newly hired teacher, limited face to face class*

Introduction

The world changed rapidly because of the COVID-19 pandemic. When the pandemic hit the world, no one was prepared. The COVID-19 pandemic has caused global damage, affecting almost every element of human life, and it became a global pandemic in March 2020, as declared by the World Health Organization (WHO). When face-to-face classes resumed, students and teachers struggled to deal with the reality of the classroom situation. The new standard setup was challenging for all the teachers, especially the newly hired ones. Since freshly hired teachers are still honing their skills, classroom management an essential aspect of teaching in which teachers must be aware of every circumstance in the classroom. Students' disruptive behavior must be corrected positively. In this situation when they are still adjusting to implementing a limited face-to-face classroom setup, poses as a challenge to new teachers. (Cabello, 2022; Delbo et al., 2023; Duplon et al., 2022; Nisar et al., 2022).

Furthermore, the Philippines has been one of Asia's directly impacted by the coronavirus's long-term and global spread. As of this writing, the country had the highest number of COVID-19 cases in Southeast Asia, breaking Indonesia's record on August 6, 2020. The spread of the COVID-19 outbreak was transmitted negatively through the educational system on various levels. Apart from the employment sector, the pandemic caused unprecedented concerns in the field of education. The future remains uncertain if the virus spreads and infects more people worldwide (Moralista & Oducado, 2020; Zhang & Ma, 2020).

Moreover, due to the ongoing crisis, the global education system faced tremendous challenges, especially for newly hired teachers. Teachers are among the most important contributors and influencers in the educational system. Conducting a study on educators' lived experiences may provide insights into additional training for teacher candidates, design creative solutions for educational leaders and teachers for future similar events and inform other stakeholders in the academic field. This unanticipated disruption in the education system had an impact on how the newly hired teachers prepared classes and delivered instruction (Allo, 2020; Isenee et al., 2020; Neubauer et al., 2019; Ngwacho, 2020; Ravindran et al., 2021; Turner et al., 2020).

The current COVID-19 outbreak has created a dilemma for some parents in considering whether to allow their children to undergo the limited face-to-face class, as well as for the teachers who will do the preparations. The government presented and laid out some beneficial strategies to ease and comprehend the diverse learning obstacles among students and parents by gathering evidence of difficulties faced by newly hired teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic (Allo, 2020; Garbe et al., 2020; Layali & Al-Shlowiy, 2020).

However, as a public high school teacher, everything was new and different for me, as it was for millions of students throughout the Philippines. Because it was unexpected, none of us could have predicted it. As a good educator, the researcher's experience with distance learning was challenging. The researcher created a personality that will work in the new set of environments. As a newly hired teacher, the researcher prepared for the limited face-to-face class and immediately re-configured the classrooms to accommodate a new learning environment (Cipriano et al., 2020; Talidong & Taquero, 2020).

Self-awareness was crucial in identifying and processing complicated feelings. The fact that politicians and even certain members of the public who misunderstood teachers' hesitation to return to class showed that teachers' perspectives on the situation are undervalued. Understanding teachers' thoughts and sentiments was crucial as they implemented the limited face-to-face class. The newly hired teachers also maintained communication channels with parents and students to monitor and to timely respond to their needs. Given the significant changes in education due to the pandemic, understanding the experiences and challenges of newly hired teachers may provide insight into what they require during the limited face-to-face classes. This study was conducted in one of the district schools in General Santos City. As a result, this phenomenological study aimed to explore and comprehend the challenges encountered by newly hired teachers during the limited face-to-face education (Gewertz, 2020; Maguire & McNamara, 2020; Turner et al., 2020).

Research Questions

The researcher conducted a phenomenological study to understand the challenges of the newly hired teachers in participating in limited face-to-face education. Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. How do the newly hired teachers describe the challenges during the limited face-to-face education?
 - 1.1. How do the newly hired teachers experience the limited face-to-face education?
 - 1.2. How do newly hired teachers cope with the challenges of limited face-to-face education?
 - 1.3. What insights do newly hired teachers gain from limited face-to-face education?

Methodology

Research Design

This study aimed to explore the thoughts and feelings of the newly hired teachers about the challenges during the limited face-to-face education. The study used a phenomenological methodological approach to pursue this qualitative study to understand teachers' interpretive experience of their reflective processes as they know and understand their students' learning. Investigate human subjects' lived experiences of an event. Using a phenomenological design is essential for learning from the experiences of others. Experiences, perceptions, and a detailed description from individuals who witnessed the event are relevant criteria for validating the choice of phenomenological design. A phenomenological design's primary goal is to describe the meaning of an experience based on what happened and how human subjects perceived the event. It was claimed that the qualitative methods are appropriate for comprehending the meaning, interpretation, and construction of participants' subjective experiences. The qualitative data were obtained through semi-structured interviews with participants, which the researcher transcribed. It took a holistic approach to this study and the integrated report to fully understand the situation (Neubauer et al., 2019).

Furthermore, qualitative research designs are frameworks for investigating an event in a natural setting. The decision to use a phenomenological design was based on the research questions and the purpose of the study. Qualitative researchers use two designs: grounded theory and phenomenology. A phenomenological design is used to understand the in-depth dimensions of an event from the perspectives of those who lived it. Grounded theory design is a subjective inquiry based on participants' perspectives in developing a theory. The methodologies were elaborated upon, as well as the data analysis and the assessments of trustworthiness, constraints, and ethical assurances. As stated by Erikson's adult stage of human development theory, administrators must know that the COVID-19 global pandemic threatened teachers' social and emotional development. Participants were interviewed in semi-structured interviews, which subsequently was transcribed by the researcher (Ataro, 2020; Busetto et al., 2020; Burns & Peacock, 2019; DeJonckheere & Vaughn, 2019; Denzin & Lincoln, 2018).

Participants

The researcher based the sampling strategy on a purposeful sample approach in this qualitative research. The phenomenon of interest here was the challenges faced by newly hired teachers during their limited face-to-face education. The researcher purposely included the participants of this study, who were twenty (20) newly hired teachers participating in the conduct of limited face-to-face education. Purposive sampling is a technique in which researchers use their discretion to select a sample that they believe, based on prior knowledge, will provide the necessary data. This method prevents researchers from simply studying anyone available Hidayanti et al. (2018). Moreover, the researcher ensured that proper health protocols were followed during the study's implementation.

In addition, the researcher concentrated on the challenges faced by (20) newly hired teachers, limiting the number of participants to a minimum so that I could pay great attention to the specifics of their subjective experiences. Additionally, some Focus Group Discussions took place in the four corners of their classrooms, and some took place in the actual schools. As per Adams et al. (2017), the focus group method involves gathering a group of people to discuss a subject matter to discover not only the participants' beliefs about it but also their thought processes and the reasons behind their beliefs. As emphasized that care was taken among the participants to ensure that none of the information gathered would embarrass them participants; in other words, confidentiality should be observed significantly when the difficulties narrated may affect their relationship with others.

Procedure

In the conduct of the study, the researcher sent a research proposal to the Office of the Graduate Studies for ethical review; once the office sent their approval, he requested an endorsement letter from the RMMC-General Santos Graduate School through the office of the Dean to conduct the study; then, he sent a letter to the validators for them to validate the interview guide questions; letter of invitation with the informed consent form approved by the RMMC-Graduate School was sent to the informants. The researcher explained to the respondents of the study's primary purpose and that their participation was voluntary.

The researcher underwent the following procedures: In-depth interviews with research informants, focus group discussions with participants, and note-taking. The researcher ensured ethical concerns were followed before conducting in-depth interviews with the study participants. The researcher used permission and confidentiality, two crucial ethical considerations that should be measured in any research. The researcher ensured the interview occurred in a quiet area with plenty of privacy and no distractions. An in-depth interview was applied. It allowed the researcher to understand the participant's views on the research issue.

In addition, in-depth interviews should also be conducted comprehensively to ensure reliability and validity, which are important concepts in qualitative research. To accomplish sound conclusions, focus on factual data presented by the participants throughout the interview to eliminate any bias or misunderstandings about the outcomes.

All sessions and informants were treated with confidentiality. The researcher also informed them that there might be additional questions aside from the interview guide if the researcher thinks of any necessary insights into the study.

In conclusion, the researcher ensured that the listening concepts were observed during the data collection. The researcher allowed the participants to use any technology they wanted, such as a phone and laptop if they promised that everything that happened during the interview and group discussions would be kept strictly confidential. The data results were transcribed, analyzed, and interpreted confidentially; the researcher also ensured that the data were saturated. Finally, the findings were summarized to arrive at the implications, recommendations for future researchers, and concluding remarks. The researcher plans to publish the results and findings in an online journal for further dissemination.

Data Analysis

The researcher intended to break down all the data acquired to comprehend it better so that each component may be arranged correctly and given the appropriate explanation and meaning. Data was gathered through semi-structured interviews. Open-ended questions allowed participants to express their experiences related to the phenomena being examined. In qualitative research, data analysis is segmenting data from transcripts, looking for trends, and assigning codes to the research question. Themes were assigned when the patterns had been recognized and coded.

The researchers supplemented audio-tape interviews with field notes folders to ensure newly hired teachers' data was analyzed during limited face-to-face classes. Field notes assisted the researcher in comprehending the significance of audio-taped data and keeping track of critical situational elements during data analysis. Qualitative content analysis aims to discover fundamental consistencies and meanings. Thematic analysis, a type of sorting and categorizing, was described as this matching and shelving material.

There were two categories of stories: ones that were uplifting and ones that were dismal. Data presentation is organizing and presenting data in graphic organizers such as matrices, charts, and graphs that allow the viewer to conclude. At this point, other higher-order categories not discovered during the initial data reduction step emerged. The last steps of qualitative analysis were to draw conclusions and verify them. A logical framework of related ideas was used to organize these thoughts. The conclusion was straightforward and accurate, correctly differentiating which information was a factual description and which was the researcher's own opinion. An excellent analysis gives enough explanation to allow the reader to comprehend the basis for an interpretation, as well as enough interpretation to allow the reader to understand the description.

Results and Discussion

This section presented the findings of the study based on the gathered data taken from the participants.

Participants

This study included 20 participants who taught elementary, high, and senior high school. Nine (9) male and eleven (11) female teachers were newly hired in late 2020. They were selected based on their years of teaching experience in their respective schools. Focus Group. Two focus group discussions were held, each with five participants (nine females and one male). They were all chosen in the same manner as the participants and came from elementary and high school schools. Participants in the focus groups had teaching experiences ranging from less than a year to three years since 2020. The use of the participant's real names during the discussion was avoided to cover up the identity of the participants. They were also assigned screen names. Both research groups responded to the same set of questions. They were my friends, so I discovered the similarity of our experiences in the limited face-to-face education journey during our get-together. With the assistance of their school principals and colleagues,

The first group for Focus Group Discussion was Fatima National High School teachers. It consisted of five enthusiastic informants.

Teacher T is a 25-year-old teacher. She was teaching grade 10 and 1 year and six months in service. On the other hand, Teacher S is 24 years 24-year-old educator, one year and eight months in service, who successfully teaches grade 8. Similarly, Teacher R is 26 and has been in that station for one year, teaching grade 7. Moreover, Teacher O is 26 years old, has two years in service, and is teaching grade 10. Further, the last participant for the FGD on this station is Teacher N. She is 28 years old, has been in service for one year and ten months, and is beautifully teaching grade 8.

Secondly, the following participants for the Focus Group Discussion came from NASA Elementary School and Upper Tumbler Central Elementary School 1. The data collection was taken from five brilliant and bright informants consisting of one male and four females. Teacher Q is a 26-year-old teacher who has been teaching for grade 4. Further, Teacher M is a 26-year-old teacher whose service has reached two years. Likewise, Teacher P has also served the institution for one year and 11 months. She is a 26-year-old female teacher. Similarly, Teacher L rendered two years of service. She is a 25-year-old enthusiastic educator. Further, the last informant was the only male in the group, a 27-year-old Teacher K, who has been serving the school for years as one year and ten months. Furthermore, their relationship with my friends assisted me greatly in making the information more understandable. All informants in the in-depth interview were my friends, but some of the participants in the Focus Group Discussion (FGD) were referred to me. They were very cooperative in answering all my interview questions. Because of their limited face-to-face education, one could still feel happiness and despair through their voices and facial gestures.

Moreover, the focus group discussion was fascinating, and the interaction was unexpected. The researcher ensured that they signed the consent certificate and that all equipment, such as audio tapes, my phone's recorder, and pen audio recorders, was used with the assurance that everything that occurred during the interview and group discussions would be kept confidential. To strengthen their trust and confidence, all the tapes recorded will be played for them to listen to, and if there are any issues they wish to be deleted, they should be. Even the recorded notes will be shown to them for review and approval. This process aimed to create a secure and open environment, encouraging honest and reflective sharing. Additionally, the researcher highlighted the importance of participant feedback to maintain the integrity of the study.

Categorization of Data

All the data that was gathered was examined. The researcher organized all the data to make it easier to interpret. This made it possible to properly explain and emphasize the importance of each component while also placing it in the correct order. Data analysis in research investigations requires summarizing the large amount of data collected and conveying the main conclusions, according to Thomas et al. (2022). In a similar vein, the methodology for data analysis will comprise data visualization, data reduction, conclusion drafting, and verification. Data reduction involves abstracting information from transcriptions, eliminating unnecessary information, and condensing the information into a form that is accessible to a wide audience. To handle the data, the researcher used the expertise of a qualified data analyst, especially for organizing and classifying large volumes of qualitative data and for finding and locating words and phrases. Once the data had been sorted and classified, it was consolidated and made manageable. The data that the participants supplied was categorized and grouped into themes that emerged in terms of experiences, coping strategies, and insights (Akinyode & Khan, 2018).

Data display, on the other hand, is the organization of data and its presentation in the form of graphic organizers such as matrices, charts, graphs, and tables that allow the viewer to draw conclusions. Qualifying and making conclusions were the last steps in the qualitative analysis process. Although the process of verification is closely related to the process of drawing conclusions. Verification involves going back to the data and confirming or reexamining its findings, while consideration involves analyzing the implications of the data analysis for the questions that were originally posed (Johnson et al., 2020; Mezmir, 2020).

Before formulating a cogent case in the clearest manner possible to enable others to evaluate the study's validity, the researcher considered several alternative interpretations Alase (2017). When analyzing the report, the researcher considered which material to keep and which to ignore. In addition, the interpretation is presented in a clear, correct manner that distinguishes between information that is the researcher's viewpoint and that which is a real description. In other words, the researcher went through each subject's statements looking for ones that were particularly relevant, that seemed particularly meaningful to the participant in describing his or her experience in relation to the phenomenon of interest, as the participants replayed in their minds the experiences that had been recorded during the interview sessions.

The Experiences of Newly Hired Teachers During the Limited Face-to-Face Education

The data collected on the experiences of the study participants revealed six emergent themes, as presented in Table 1. These themes are Rejoicing in the Reopening of Classes, Anticipating Challenges, Collaborating with Initiatives, Adhering to the Protocol, Meticulous in Tasking, and Efficient Communication.

Rejoicing in the Reopening of Classes

The researcher revealed that the Newly hired teachers during the limited face-to-face class was happy and nervous because it was finally a face-to-face class. At first, the newly hired teacher was worried since not all the learners were fully vaccinated.

Participants narrated that prior to implementing the limited face-to-face classes, there were seminars conducted about hybrid classes,

and they were happy because, after two years, the students could finally return to school.

Table 1. *The Experiences of Newly Hired Teachers During the Limited Face-to-Face Education*

Cluster Themes	Emergent Themes
Feeling excited for the job I felt happy Ready for the job Intense preparation Felt anxious for the challenge Scared for what will happen Our school is not ready for it I'm not quite confident	Rejoicing in the Reopening of Classes
Conversing with colleagues Keep in touch with colleagues Doing things correctly Prioritizing the time schedules	Anticipating Challenges
Discussion of health protocol Putting efforts in planning Implementation of social distancing. Proper implementation of rules and regulations	Collaborating with Initiatives
Working with grace and time management Task distribution was planned Tasks are properly organized Tasks are equally distributed	Adhering the Protocol
Proper engagement with workmate I talk and I share my ideas Listening to other comments Ensuring courtesy with colleagues	Meticulous in Tasking
	Efficient Communication

Anticipating Challenges

The newly hired teacher pointed out that planning to implement limited face-to-face class had always been considered. Safety protocol or safety measures must be considered primary. Preparing the school, especially the classrooms, and all the necessary things for the safety of the students was a must. The preparations were very intense. Everyone was very busy, especially during classroom preparations.

Collaborating with Initiatives

Prioritizing the well-being of colleagues and the public is imperative. To stop the virus from spreading, everyone should be well. It is important to always maintain good cleanliness and getting the COVID-19 vaccine would be a great approach to demonstrate to our coworkers that we are concerned about their health. By now, teamwork had also become rather important. Always strike up a discussion. All parties are informed and supported when there are open lines of communication. A safer atmosphere can be created by promoting a culture of shared accountability and consideration. Furthermore, maintaining general wellbeing depends on the availability of mental health resources.

Adhering to the Protocol

Extra challenge for the newly hired Teacher, considering that there was a plan to implement face-to-face classes. The protocols must be followed for everyone's safety and well-being. They informed immediately if there was an important matter from the division regarding safety and protocols. Reality is what always makes an idealistic approach challenging. The regulations and school protocols are clearly stated.

Meticulous in Tasking

The tasks were changed based on the teacher's level of expertise. Some teachers now have an even worse scenario where they must accomplish more than others because of these. An unequal workforce resulted from the necessity to distribute the tasks. It was also revealed that the school heads found the undertaking to be quite challenging. Everyone at the school, it was said—experienced educators as well as recently hired ones—was busy. Staff members occasionally become frustrated and burned out because of this imbalance in workload. To address these issues, group problem-solving sessions were arranged. Finding a just and effective method to divide up the workload continued to be the administration's primary focus.

Efficient Communication

The teacher participants had gone a lot in this limited face-to-face class. Nevertheless, most of them had faith in the capabilities of their

colleagues. On the edge of toughness, they still managed to see the competence of their teaching force. Amidst difficulties and conflicts, if there were things that needed to be done or things that should be done, communicating with them was the first step. Sometimes, they initiated a conversation with them. Eventually, Teacher pointed out that he interacted with them appropriately if they had ample time to know them.

The Coping Mechanism of Newly Hired Teachers During the Limited Face-to-Face Education

The data collected regarding the research's challenges revealed six emergent themes, as presented in Table 2. These themes are Requesting Assistance, Receiving Compliments, Sharing Commitment, Emanating Positivity and Growth, Open Communication, and Developing Success.

Table 2. *The Coping Mechanism of Newly Hired Teachers During the Limited Face-to-Face Education*

Cluster Themes	Emergent Themes
Engaging to social activities Soliciting ideas Embrace possible changes Seeking for Support	Requesting for Assistance
Recognizing efforts. Good Output based on the plan Importance of hardwork and Selfless Delegation of tasks	Receiving Compliments
Personal and grupop Responsibilities Action over Duties Shared Obligations Maintaining positive mindset	Sharing of Commitment
Engaging positivity Working with mentors Conducive and healthy environment Personal Growth and Development	Eminating Positivity and Growth
Diverse communication Working Together Respect decisions Understanding one another	Open Communication
Valuing Leadership Working with common goal Unity for success Appreciation for kindness	Developing Success

Requesting Assistance

The newly hired teachers tried to do their work correctly due to the wellness of their jobs. They were responsible and had the initiative to make work more favorable. They also considered that they had a good relationship with their colleagues. Engaging in social activities to prepare and to face new challenges like the new working environment, and gradually adapting to a new learning environment. So, as a newly hired teacher they created a positive change by immediately identifying learning gaps, for instance, by providing various assessments to students.

Receiving Compliments

Every teacher has responsibilities, whether in the classroom or outside. The teacher should be flexible. They should think quickly when addressing the concerns of his / her fellow teachers. Partly, the teacher narrated that everyone is hardworking and selfless. It was not easy, but for the students, they will do everything. The teachers exerted effort in doing their instructional materials and teaching methods.

Sharing of Commitment

Being good to others was valuable. Indeed, the teacher believed that the priority or responsibility that they needed was to focus on the classroom. The primary responsibility that they had was to become advisers. It became challenging, and although it was a difficult job, at the same time, it was fulfilling, especially when they saw their students having a good grade and a good attitude. Also, it felt satisfying when they knew that those students who were unruly before became proper and hustled hard and finished their studies. As an educator, her role or responsibility was to ensure that her learners stayed actively engaged and maintained their motivation.

Emanating Positivity and Growth

The teacher described how they strive to achieve their goals. Their primary focus of concern were teaching, discipline, and having a positive outlook. They should also be in good health, having reached financial, mental, emotional, and physical maturity. Working with

experienced teachers on any relevant school improvement was the biggest achievement. The secret to their success was creating a cooperative and encouraging atmosphere. Instructors frequently exchanged cutting-edge techniques and best practices to enhance their pedagogical approaches. Through opportunities for ongoing learning and development, both professional and personal growth were promoted. Their shared objectives and sense of camaraderie reinforced their dedication to offering high-quality instruction.

Open Communication

Camaraderie creates companionship toward success, and fostering success creates consideration. The teacher elaborated to always have excellent or proper communication with colleagues, ask for something vague to clarify things. The teacher agreed that they collaborated with their colleagues by doing the assigned task. As a result, they built a good relationship with fellow educators.

Developing Success

As stated, always give without remembering and receive without forgetting. On this matter, the teacher pointed out that parents should be more aware of what is happening inside the classrooms. As advisers and teachers, the instructors maintained appropriate communication with the learners' parents and guardians to guarantee the students' well-being and safety throughout the few in-person lessons. Regular updates and feedback sessions were conducted to keep parents informed about their child's progress and any concerns. Engaging parents in school activities and decision-making processes fostered a sense of community and shared responsibility. Teachers also provided resources and guidance to help parents support their children's learning at home. This collaborative approach ensured a holistic support system for the students, enhancing their overall educational experience.

The Insights of Newly Hired Teachers During the Limited Face-to-Face Education

From the data collected on the insights that the teachers can share to others about their experiences during the limited face to face class as newly hired teachers; six emergent themes appeared as presented at table 3. These themes are: Receptive to Feedback, Valuing Responsibilities, Accepting Imperfections, Proficiency in Decision Making, Possessing Empathy and Kindness, Enhancing Instructional Methods.

Table 3. *The Insights of Newly Hired Teachers During the Limited Face-to-Face Education*

Cluster Themes	Emergent Themes
Prioritizing important things Flexible in everything Manageable and bearable Era Open for suggestions Willingness to learn new things	Receptive to Feedback
Learning to value work Satisfaction and contentment Know well your assigned task Sharing of knowledge and capabilities	Valuing Responsibilities
Learn how to be patient Able to multitasks Learn to accept mistakes Know your limitations	Accepting Imperfections
Providing quality education Guided during the preparation Following orders and memorandum Adjustments and changes	Proficiency in Decision Making
Adapting workflow Create positive environment Waiting for the right time Learn to foregive and forget	Possessing Empathy and Kindness
Proper planning is the best Think positive for success Valuing time management Settled issues for success Make yourself prepared	Enhancing Instructional Methods

Receptive to Feedback

For an undefined amount of time, researchers who develop the capacity to consistently gain new and improved kinds of understanding that they may use in their work and lives will be influential members of our society. As they said it was always more fun and productive if classes were done physically that is why they make sure that the institution was pleased with whatever the result of this program saying that there were things that needed to be considered.

On this matter, the teacher and the researcher emphasized that all teachers should make an extra effort in teaching the students so that they can fill the gap left by the modular learning that occurred two years ago, which was a completely new experience for them because

it was their first-time teaching, and it was also during a pandemic.

Valuing Responsibilities

Appreciation is a beautiful thing. People with an appreciative mindset often see the message in chaos they find reasons to get back up after being knocked down by life. Positivity was always one of the most critical factors in completing the task. According to Herzberg (2017), the most common factors that lead to job satisfaction are motivation, achievement, and work quality. In contrast, a positive approach results from behavior and performance.

Accepting Imperfections

As a researcher, I believe that love is the commendation and adoring of the amiable qualities of the beloved person upon the condition of being the object of their action. Several teachers agreed that doing your part effectively will contribute a lot to the development of the tasks. Unquestionably, patience and understanding were critical in getting through it all. Be responsible. Collaborative approach and sharing are essential because no one can do it alone. There is no turning back, so we could enjoy.

Proficiency in Decision Making

The researcher believes that creativity is the most critical human resource. Without creativity, there would be no progress, and we would forever repeat the same patterns. The teacher stated that they must find different ways, strategies, and techniques to deliver our lessons. They should fit the students' current knowledge because they are different. They can only use a different strategy for some, especially now that they are all at the extremes.

Possessing Empathy and Kindness

It was about how people treat one another. It talked about human dignity. We forced the employers to treat us as equals, to sit down and talk to us about the work we do, how we do it, and what we get paid for it. As the teacher said, they should give time to the students to master the basics. However, educators needed to adapt quickly as new plans and learning interventions were being developed to address the student's learning gaps. Technological integration makes the lesson interesting and enjoyable, and teachers remain optimistic even if they are already tired of their jobs.

Enhancing Instructional Methods

The researcher believe that freedom is a fundamental human right. Independence entails accountability. This was frightening for the person unwilling to grow up and not wanting to carry his weight. The teacher emphasized that this endeavor affected her, asking her many "what ifs" questions. Later, though, she understood that she needed to focus on the positive aspect and how to make the most of it rather than overwhelming themselves with these questions. Undeniably, they served as role models in part because they were teachers. This endeavor taught the researcher about being a teacher, especially in a small face-to-face class.

Major Findings

The findings highlighted various experiences of newly hired teachers participating in limited face-to-face classes. The study revealed mixed feelings of happiness and nervousness among teachers as they transitioned back to in-person teaching. Initial concerns included the fact that not all learners were fully vaccinated. However, the Department of Education reassured teachers about the implementation of health standards within school premises, which helped alleviate some worries. Participants expressed excitement about face-to-face classes, believing it would enhance students' understanding. Despite this, some teachers questioned the feasibility and safety of limited face-to-face classes, fearing a potential resurgence of COVID-19. Teachers A and L emphasized the importance of rigorous planning and safety measures for face-to-face interactions. Intense preparations, especially for classroom setups, were necessary to ensure student safety. Teacher T also noted that Upper Tumbler Central Elementary School 1 faced numerous requirements before gaining approval to conduct face-to-face classes.

The well-being of all staff members and colleagues was prioritized, emphasizing the importance of maintaining good health to prevent the spread of COVID-19. Proper hygiene practices and vaccination were strongly encouraged as measures to protect everyone's health. Collaboration among teachers was crucial during this period. Teacher S, who initially found it challenging to interact with others due to her introverted nature, expressed gratitude towards her colleagues for their supportive approach.. These conversations are not necessarily work-related; casual ones will do. Maintaining well-being is also essential because they cannot perform your duties as a teacher if you are not mentally and physically fit.

Following protocols presented an additional challenge for newly hired teachers with the plan to implement face-to-face classes. Adhering to these protocols was essential for everyone's safety and well-being. Important safety updates from the division were communicated promptly. Teacher R appreciated the school's smooth implementation of regulations, feeling happy despite minor issues because, after almost two years, face-to-face classes were finally happening. Despite clear regulations and protocols, their practical implementation posed challenges, particularly in ensuring students followed them diligently. The paragraph discusses the challenges related to task distribution among teachers, highlighting issues of imbalance and the impact on both newly hired and seasoned educators. Task allocation was based on teachers' competence, leading to some feeling overburdened. This situation created tensions and required

careful management by school heads. Despite the challenges, some benefits were noted for newly hired teachers, as the experience allowed them to develop their skills.

Teachers often initiated conversations to ensure smooth operations and compliance with duties. Teacher G emphasized the importance of getting to know colleagues and following school heads' instructions to reduce stress. Newly hired teachers sought help from more experienced colleagues to meet deadlines. Teacher F highlighted the need for courteous and respectful communication. The teachers who took part in this survey were committed to their jobs and encouraged goodwill among their peers. In order to adjust to new situations and obstacles, Teacher A participated in social activities. Teacher E upheld classroom rules and encouraged student participation in school projects. Teacher C addressed these problems using a variety of exams after identifying educational gaps. To inspire children, teachers F and J used ICT strategies and rewarded good behavior. By putting money into their classrooms, loving their pupils, and offering necessary tools and assistance, Teachers K and L showed their enthusiasm and inventiveness.

The teachers demonstrated their commitment and flexibility in managing their extracurricular and classroom duties. Teacher K emphasized the importance of adaptability and rapid thinking. Teacher S conveyed her appreciation for her encouraging coworkers. Teacher J mentioned his coworkers' financial donations to classroom preparation and expressed admiration for their dedication and altruism. Teachers put in a lot of effort and sacrificed personal time on the weekends and during breaks to establish a positive learning environment, even in the face of obstacles and time constraints. They deserve special recognition for their work creating educational materials and carrying out rehabilitation plans to address academic deficits.

Teacher K underlined the significance of concentrating on classroom duties and the satisfaction that results from witnessing students' behavioral and intellectual progress. It was satisfying to be an adviser despite the difficulties. Teacher C emphasized how important it is for educators to maintain students' motivation and engagement. She had to prepare and create interesting activities to keep students interested in her lessons as a freshly recruited teacher.

Teachers K and O emphasized the importance of discipline, a positive mindset, and holistic health for achieving accomplishments. Their department ensures daily lesson plans are checked individually. Teacher A turned a desolate front yard into a colorful garden despite limited water supply. Teacher B, a newly hired teacher, valued working with seasoned colleagues on school development and accepted challenging tasks with gratitude, learning important lessons. Similarly, Teacher I contributed to the school's technical team by creating digital presentations and e-materials to support student learning.

Teachers who work together and communicate openly together are more successful and considerate. Teacher M stressed the value of communicating clearly and asking for help when necessary. In order to complete their assignments successfully, Teachers A and C worked cooperatively with colleagues, seeking clarifications and assistance as needed, which fostered good connections. Teacher S emphasized the cooperative atmosphere in her department, where duties were distributed equitably and lesson ideas and PowerPoint presentations were exchanged to lessen workloads and guarantee standardized instruction in all classrooms.

Parental engagement in school activities and awareness are important, Teacher B stressed. He participated in parent-teacher conferences as a new teacher to gain a better understanding of the objectives and rules of the school. During meetings and tours of the classroom, Teacher P thanked the parents for their participation and suggestions. During the few in-person classes, teachers established excellent ties with parents and guardians despite communication challenges in order to ensure the well-being of the students. The management of traffic was another way that community stakeholders helped, and their participation was much appreciated.

Teachers who never stop searching for new ideas rise to positions of power in society. Despite obstacles, Teacher E preferred the fun and productivity of in-person instruction and strived for institutional satisfaction. Extra efforts in teaching were emphasized by Teacher G and the researcher to fill up the gaps left by modular learning during the pandemic. Due to expectations stemming from her father's journalism background, Teacher L experienced difficulties in her roles as coordinator and adviser for the school newspaper. A recently appointed teacher named Teacher T brought attention to the compromises made during modular learning and the misconceptions surrounding the work of instructors. They adjusted and handled the situation in spite of the challenges.

Appreciation and a positive mindset are crucial for teachers. Teacher B felt satisfied with positive feedback and student participation. Teacher D acknowledged the need for improvement in handling students' attitudes and learning capabilities, emphasizing the basics. Teacher I felt she could still improve and learn more about teaching and interacting with students and colleagues. Positivity was highlighted as vital for job satisfaction, motivation, and work quality. Despite the stress of limited face-to-face classes, maintaining a positive outlook and striving to satisfy students and colleagues is essential.

Teachers highlighted the value of teamwork, tolerance, and understanding in their instruction. Teacher A emphasized that the attitudes of tolerance and understanding are essential to helping students appreciate their work. In order to more accurately evaluate the learning capacities of her students, Teacher J suggested studying about their backgrounds. It was decided that accountability and teamwork were necessary. Teacher L said that in order to reduce stress, start chores early and be aware of your limitations. Teachers were urged to take pleasure in their work despite obstacles.

To succeed and stay away from recurring patterns, creativity is important. Teacher P underlined the need of using a range of tactics and approaches suited to the different knowledge levels of her students. Teachers E and F emphasized that students are the engine of

the future and urged them to realize their potential and put their education first.

Kindness and empathy are important because they emphasize treating everyone equally and with dignity. Owing to learning gaps, Teacher B emphasized the value of giving pupils time to grasp the fundamentals. Teacher C emphasized being flexible and accepting of new strategies and initiatives. Teacher H went on to say that incorporating technology into the classroom makes the material more interesting and keeps teachers optimistic even in the face of job tiredness. In general, the theme is to be kind to others, change rapidly, and make use of technology to improve education.

The paragraph emphasizes on the duties that go along with improving teaching strategies and how important it is. In addition to highlighting freedom as a human right connected to accountability, it quotes Barbara Jordan on the importance of national unity. It talks about a difficult but ultimately uplifting path toward a constructive perspective and attention to the good things in life. In order to be taken seriously as role models, teachers need to be aware of what they do, especially on social media, and be ready for anything that may come up in in-person classroom settings. The paragraph considers educational and personal development learning events in general.

Implications for Practice

This study covered the participants' lived experiences at a specific institution, with the following implications:

Rejoicing in the reopening of classes. We know that people have different emotions, and we also need to consider or understand them. Since they maintain motivation, happy feelings might support students' prolonged engagement with the material (motivational impact). If teachers have positive experiences, they are likelier to enjoy their teaching experience and develop a love for teachers. However, they must remember that teaching sometimes requires confusion and frustration when teaching difficult but necessary concepts (cognitive impact).

Anticipating Challenges. Schools faced several issues daily that negatively impact student learning. Administrators and teachers worked hard to overcome these challenges, but it was often difficult. Regardless of schools' strategy, some factors will likely never be eliminated.

Collaborating with Initiatives. Strong relationships provided a foundation for student and teacher engagement, belonging, and learning. Students are more engaged in the classroom when they develop stronger relationships with their teachers. To cultivate these relationships, schools should prioritize creating a culture that values adults fostering relationships with students and giving teachers and staff the time, space, and opportunities to regularly engage with individual students, particularly those who appear less engaged.

Adhering to the Protocol. A safe school can improve the physical and mental health of those in it. One study found that feelings of safety at school were positively related to "both behavioral and academic outcomes."

Meticulous in Tasking. Collaborative learning is becoming increasingly crucial in both businesses and classrooms. The study discovered that educators who assumed accountability in the classroom developed into more active rather than passive participants. Teachers became much more willing and, over time, comfortable taking on individual responsibilities. The researcher discovered that teachers with classroom-assigned tasks and responsibilities developed strong work ethics throughout the school year.

Efficient Communication. Every educator in this society has low points. Some may handle or even hide them better than others. However, the truth is, whatever we are going through, others have been through it, too. We are not alone. Try to stay in touch with your family, friends, and coworkers. In any situation, especially at work, express your emotions and worries.

They are requesting for Assistance. Skills have become essential thinking skills for teachers and students. These skills trained teachers to think creatively and systematically to produce innovative thinking. Teachers or someone who uses lateral thinking will create new ideas from ideas already known in solving problems. As Yıldız et al. (2020) and Beyaz (2020) said late, actual thinking tendencies have found significant correlations between lateral thinking, critical thinking, and conscious awareness.

Receiving Compliments. Teacher performance assessment has emerged as a central subject in initiatives to reform schools. Teachers were very productive and motivated in planning, even though the resources were insufficient. They managed. The teachers hesitated during the limited face-to-face class but had no choice. They fostered sound output.

Sharing of Commitment. As a researcher, when it comes to commitment, the researcher found that teachers provided the love, desire, and energy they needed to perform better. Teachers and the school developed an emotional bond in the few face-to-face classes due to the willingness to support the institution, which encouraged teachers to look for methods to improve their teaching and create a productive learning environment to help students meet their goals. Similarly, committed teachers' passion was caring and learning new things, especially during the pandemic.

Emanating Positivity and Growth. As for the teachers and parents, they needed to know what constituted a flourishing life, what contributed to it, and what did not, and they were expected to act in a way that enabled their children to lead a flourishing life. Discipline and a good mindset are the things that a teacher must be primarily focused on. They should also be healthy and holistically – physically, mentally, financially, and emotionally ready. As Pressley (2021) said, teachers are not returning to what was thought of as a "regular"

classroom setting prior to the pandemic outbreak.

Open Communication. Teachers demonstrating compassion for their students differed from wanting them to like them. Many new teachers make the mistake of wanting their pupils' approval, mainly when working with older kids who were close in age. However, this can result in a lack of respect for one another. Furthermore, in the brief in-person classes, demonstrating empathy for the students only required a little time and effort as we continued to make decisions that would optimize their educational experience. Showing compassion does not mean we are a student's friend, but it rather shows means we care about their progress and are invested in their future.

Developing Success. During the pandemic, teacher education programs must consider how they prepare teachers to enter the ever-changing field of education. The study results showed the importance of self-efficacy in teachers' knowledge and skills of content. It was evident that the pandemic did not adversely affect teachers who already had a high level of self-efficacy prior to transitioning to online instruction. As teachers in a new generation, we must be more advanced and innovative in all aspects of education.

Receptive to Feedback. As a researcher, the researcher observed that the teachers' journey was difficult and rough, but everything came to be done with effort and time. We must consider some factors that will support our plans to achieve them. This experience helped the Teacher improve communication and classroom management skills.

Valuing Responsibilities. Teachers participating in the limited face-to-face classes should also be given appreciation. This did not mean teachers had to become 'personal' with the administrations. Instead, it helped the teachers be open about their appreciation of what the administration does for them and the school. Expressing even a little appreciation goes a long way.

Accepting Imperfections. As teachers, we should be kind to other people around us, especially to our colleagues. Considering that, as of this time, we were adjusting to our present situation after the COVID-19 Pandemic. We must know our limitations. If we cannot do the task, do not accept it. If we accept it, we will get stressed, you will get sick, and you will be the person who will be affected. Aside from that, we must enjoy it even if the job is tiring. There is no turning back, so we could enjoy.

Proficiency in Decision Making. Learning is a continuous process. As teachers, we had to follow the school's rules in general. Also, we had to improve our lessons and be more innovative. We had to find different ways, strategies, and techniques for delivering the lessons. We had to enroll in postgraduate studies to expand our knowledge and pedagogy. Learning about the trends in education will create a stronghold for effective teachers in the new normal.

Possessing Empathy and Kindness. The most significant learning acquired from newly hired teachers' challenges was learning to accommodate changes. There may be uncertainties as they take the journey in the education system. However, as educators, it is vital to adapt quickly to new plans and learning interventions to develop and address the learning gaps of our students. As teachers, we must be an instrument to bring back the students' passion for learning and be patient in all aspects of education, considering that students are the number one priority among others.

Enhancing Instructional Methods. Eventually, the limited face-to-face learning pushed the teachers to become better. Teachers must extend their patience and understanding to the different groups of students. This made the teachers think and reflect a lot, especially about teaching methods and dealing with colleagues and students. Be a good example to others and work for good.

Implications for Future Research

The intent of this study was to address several research concerns regarding the experiences of recently employed newly hired teachers when doing the limited face-to-face classroom instruction. The researcher summarizes the study's implications for foregrounding and recommends some future research topics based on the findings. Numerous options for further research, including theory formulation and concept confirmation, were brought up by this qualitative analysis. Further research would be required to polish and expound on the investigator's innovative discoveries. During the limited face-to-face class, the researcher aimed to examine teachers' opinions on understanding the challenges of newly hired teachers. Previous studies investigated teacher perceptions of remote instructing during the New Normal of the COVID-19 Pandemic, but there was a lack of research for those who attended classes or taught during the pandemic (Hester et al., 2020; Morgan, 2020)

According to previous literature and reports on COVID-19, the new teaching demands would affect all aspects of how teachers would instruct when they arrived at school. Participants were either teaching students face-to-face or using a hybrid method in which some students were physically present in the classroom while others were virtual. The significance of administrative and teaching staff who require training on how to deal with the virus, identify risks, and put appropriate measures in place for everyone's health and safety. Furthermore, future researchers may investigate how teachers and students are directly affected when participating in limited face-to-face classes during an ongoing pandemic or other crisis. This will contribute to a better understanding of how school leaders and administrators can work together to support their staff and students while implementing strategies that promote career and academic Success. By addressing these research areas, scholars can contribute valuable insights to inform policy, improve teacher education programs, and enhance the overall resilience and effectiveness of educators facing unprecedented challenges in the education landscape.

Finally, future research could include data from interviews and surveys conducted with all stakeholders, including education

administrators, school principals, support staff, students, parents, and school community members, to compare the perspectives of all those involved. Schleicher (2020) also emphasized the significance of raising public awareness about strategically employed teachers to increase parental and community support for schools and teachers.

Conclusions

According to this phenomenological qualitative study, newly hired teachers face challenges during the limited face-to-face class. These challenges were identified based on how teachers plan and prepare the physical classroom, deliver lessons, collect outputs from learners, monitor students' progress, and, most importantly, evaluate students' performance and provide feedback to students. Furthermore, understanding the challenges newly hired teachers face during the limited face-to-face education imposed by the COVID-19 pandemic is critical for fostering a resilient and adaptive education system. The unique circumstances of the pandemic have highlighted a range of issues that necessitate careful consideration, research, and targeted interventions to support educators in navigating these unprecedented times. The challenges newly hired teachers face extend beyond traditional teaching responsibilities, encompassing technology integration, remote instruction competencies, and the profound impact on teacher well-being. As we reflect on the implications of these challenges, it becomes evident that a holistic and multifaceted approach is essential to address the diverse needs of educators. Future research endeavors should explore the competencies required for effective remote teaching and propose innovative strategies for integrating them into teacher preparation programs. Additionally, a focus on teacher well-being and mental health is imperative, with studies exploring the long-term effects of the pandemic on educators' emotional resilience. Professional development needs must be reassessed to ensure newly hired teachers have the skills and knowledge necessary for successful remote instruction. Technological integration, student engagement, and assessment practices should be examined to identify best practices that can be incorporated into teacher education curricula. Collaboration and the formation of virtual professional learning communities emerge as vital components in supporting teachers during these challenging times. Furthermore, an equity lens should be applied to address the disparate impacts of remote learning on students, emphasizing the role of educators in fostering inclusive and accessible education. Policy implications also warrant attention, focusing on adapting and refining education policies to better support teachers and students in the face of unforeseen disruptions. Longitudinal studies can provide insights into the lasting effects of the pandemic on teaching practices, shedding light on potential shifts in pedagogy, assessment, and classroom dynamics. As we navigate the uncertainties of the post-pandemic education landscape, a commitment to understanding and addressing the challenges newly hired teachers face is paramount. By embracing a collaborative and research-driven approach, educators, policymakers, and researchers can work together to cultivate a resilient and adaptable education system that prepares teachers for the evolving needs of the future.

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